

Eurodoc answers to a new Magna Charta Universitatum: MCU 2020

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 28 national associations of early-career researchers from 26 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As representatives of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research and innovation in Europe.

1. Is the link to the existing MCU clear and strong enough?

The MCU 2.0 tries to establish a continuity of MCU 1.0 values and principles, as stated in #7: "the principles laid out in the Magna Charta Universitatum are as valid today as they were in 1988". To our understanding, however, several aspects of the current draft of MCU 2.0 are hindering such continuity.

In MCU 1.0 #2 and in MCU systematically 2.0 #4 teaching and research are emphasized to be inseparable. Also in MCU 1.0 it is stated "freedom in research and training is the fundamental principle of university life," principles which are repeated in the MCU 2.0 preamble together with other ones. Nevertheless, the new version is, in our view, lacking its training and teaching rightful and equal status for freedom. While there is no reference to training or research, teaching in #10 only refers to responsibility and #15 refers to duty and accountability. We are convinced that with the current threats to academic freedom, the freedom of students, researchers and academics in their training, their research and their teaching should be more visible at MCU 2.0.

Moreover, while the MCU 1.0 is written in a language reminding after-WWII conventions and declaration of human rights, e.g., MCU 1.0 #8 "A university is a trustee of the European humanist tradition", the MCU 2.0 voices a more instrumental role of higher education, e.g., MCU 2.0 #8 "promoting health, prosperity and enlightenment around the world" and shifted into subtle marketized narrations.

While MCU 1.0 stresses universities as a driving force, as in "universities will be called upon to play [the part] in a changing and increasingly international society", the MCU 2.0 seems to relinquish such inspiring ambitions. MCU 2.0 presents a more passive, mechanistic and diminished role for universities, "under constant pressure to adapt" (#6) instead of embracing and even leading the change, as well as "serving" and generating "services" (#10, #11, #15) instead of generating and transmitting new knowledge.

2. Does the landscape described reflect changes which you have seen? Do the changes described in paragraph 6 align with your experience? If not, what has been omitted or inappropriately included?

The MCU 2.0 refers to the changes that the society *has already undergone*, i.e. massification, marketization, vocationalization, instrumentalization, internationalization and globalization of science. While some of these changes have had a positive impact on universities, some have been criticized both by society and universities itself. Therefore,

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MCU 2.0 should not aim to adapt to the changes or pressures disregarding reflections on marketization and unbalanced instrumentalization of universities. Besides, and maybe now more than ever, universities should pay attention to Humanities and Social Sciences in teaching and research, even if these disciplines are not as directly profitable as other technological or biomedical sciences. In our opinion, there should be an explicit reference to this particular matter in MCU 2.0, so the rich “European humanist tradition” of which universities have been trustees for nine centuries (as stated in MCU 1.0) is not gradually lost to the pressuring societal changes of the Twenty-First Century.

Changes to the current trends are being attempted, for example, in the newest European Commission (EC) consultations for [Strategic Plan implementing the research and innovation framework programme Horizon Europe](#). “The world in the Twenty-First Century” (#7) in the EC priorities, based on their analysis of current challenges. There is a shift into academia and research balancing the needs of the business, society, Europe, and environment. We believe that if the MCU 2.0 might also take into consideration The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) which summarize the changes and needs for the modern world and discuss more than “promoting health, prosperity and enlightenment around the world” #8. At least, the concept of *sustainability* should be included among the others, and ideally should find a more central presence in the MCU 2.0. SDG will be drivers both for the research, and when seeking education by future students.

The MCU 2.0 highlights that university should be “a non-discriminatory space of tolerance and respectfulness where diversity of perspectives flourishes and where inclusivity, anchored in principles of equity and fairness, prevails” (#17) and defines the main goal that the principles of MCU 2.0 ‘must be translated into action’ (#7). In spite of these references, we believe that the issues pertaining to education-related migration (i.e., displaced students, doctoral candidates, researchers and academic staff) are not addressed in MCU 2.0.

3. Does the MCU 2.0 recognise and fit with the mission of your university? Does the draft MCU 2020 accurately reflect the challenges which your university faces or anticipates?

The 21st university fulfills its main 3 missions, and research mission is one of the core, especially in the reality of global competition and rankings, while university faces massification and marketization challenges. However, the position of the university nowadays is defined by its research outputs and achievements of the university staff. As Eurodoc represents doctoral candidates and junior researchers who become future academic staff and research employees at the universities, we advocate for mentioning in the MCU 2.0 the role of the future academics and the need for improvement of their working conditions as well as career prospects for better fulfilling the university mission.

We find it very important that MCU 2.0 recognises “research and teaching must be intellectually and morally independent of all political influence and economic interests”, talks about teaching and research inseparability, and “free enquiry and debate, distinguished by

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its openness to dialogue and rejection of intolerance” (#4). These principles refer in a very satisfactory way to quality of higher education and research.

We consider of the utmost importance that MCU 2.0 explicitly acknowledges university education as a human right and a public good. That means that university must aim to openly provide knowledge and intellectual development to the general public, and does not simply train labour force for the situational demands of the labour market, as we often hear in some manipulative political speeches. In this regard, we encourage the introduction of Open Science and Open Education principles to the MCU 2.0.

Moreover, we find quite important to mention in MCU 2.0 the significance of research integrity and academic ethics for 21st-century university mission. We strongly recommend to address this matter in MCU 2.0.

<p>4. Are there any additional comments that you would like the review group to consider? Do the proposed values align well with the values and mission of your university?</p>
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We appreciate #12 reference to university’s responsibilities to society and a call for governments and society at large to recognize and defend universities and their freedoms. It is a powerful statement necessary in the current socio-political environment.

We are very satisfied with #17 description of universities as spaces of tolerance, respect, inclusion, equity, and fairness. We fully support the MCU commitment to “*education as a human right*, a public good, and available to all”. We, therefore, believe that education, as a core human right and a core value for Eurodoc, that the right to education is fully exercised when education is of *adequate quality* as stated, for example, in Recommendation CM/Rec (2012)13 of the Council of Europe. We would appreciate such a direct link in the MCU 2.0.

We think the document should mention also an online education, distant learning, global collaboration in higher education, the European universities initiative, as well as creating healthy academic environment and efficient training for doctoral candidates and new academics.

The review was elaborated by (in alphabetical order):

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Signed by Eva Hnatkova [[President European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers \(Eurodoc\)](#)] on 15 September 2019.

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